

JURISPRUDENCE

THE SUBJECT AS A CONSTITUTIVE ELEMENT OF THE CRIME OF HUMAN CLONING

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Abstract

This paper includes information about subject as a constitutive elements of the crime of human cloning, a crime against human genome. The author tries to identify the circle of person who could committ the crime of human cloning. Also, the author analyzes whether the legal entity could be subject to the crime of cloning of the human cloning crime. Finally, the author tries to determine the status of human clones.

Keywords: human genome, genetic manipulations, human cloning, subject of crime.

Introduction. According to the Universal Declaration on the Human Genome and Human Rights: „the human genome underlies the fundamental unity of all members of the human family, as well as the recognition of their inherent dignity and diversity. In a symbolic sense, it is the heritage of humanity”.¹

Intensive research into the structures that make up the hereditary material granted possibilities for scientists to intervene in the human genome and carry out genetic manipulations.

At the same time, these researches opened the way for committing antisocial acts and crimes against humanity, against the life and health of the person (like human cloning, etc.).

One of the crimes that attack the human genome is human cloning. According to the Additional Protocol to the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine, on the Prohibition of Cloning Human Beings: „Any intervention seeking to create a human being genetically identical to another human being, whether living or dead, is prohibited.”²

In this research, the author aims to identify the circle to identify the circle of person who could committ the crime of human cloning. Also, the author analyzes whether the legal entity could be subject to the crime of cloning of the human cloning crime. Finally, the author tries to determine the status of human clones.

Materials used and applied methods.

The author studied and used the international, regional and national normative framework that ensures the legal protection of human genome, as well as a vast

doctrinal framework in the field of genetics and criminal law. Also, the author used the following methods were used: logical, comparative, analysis and synthesis, systemic.

Results obtained and discussions.

Human cloning is defined as: „genetic process by which identical copies of the same individual can be obtained.”³

In accordance with the provisions of the Additional Protocol to the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine, on the Prohibition of Cloning Human Beings: „(2) For the purpose of this article, the term human being "genetically identical" to another human being means a human being sharing with another the same nuclear gene set.”

In accordance with the provisions of art. 21 (1) Criminal Code of the Republic of Moldova: "The subject of the crime is a responsible person, who during the commission of the crime reached the age established by law for criminal liability".⁴

According to the commentary to the Criminal Code: "the subject of the crime of cloning can be any responsible physical person who has reached the age of 16, regardless of whether he is a citizen of the Republic of Moldova, a foreign citizen or a person without citizenship".⁵

Mandatory signs of the subject of the crime component "cloning" are the following: physical person, responsibility, reaching the age of criminal responsibility.

¹ Universal Declaration UNESCO on the Human Genome and Human Rights. 11.11.1997. Available: <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/universal-declaration-human-genome-and-human-rights>. art.1

² Additional Protocol to the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine, on the Prohibition of Cloning Human Beings 12.01.1998. Art.1(1). Available: <https://rm.coe.int/168007f2ca>

³ BOAGHI, V. Clonarea ființelor umane: problemă etică, morală și juridică. În: Revista Națională de Drept, 2004, nr. 6, p.52

⁴ Codul Penal al Republicii Moldova: Nr. 985 din 18.04.2002. În: Monitorul Oficial al Republicii Moldova, 14.04.2009, nr. 72-74. Art.21

⁵ BARBĂNEAGRĂ, A., ALECU, GH., BERLIBA, V., BUDECI, V., CARPOV, T., CUȘNIR, V., COJOCARU, R., MARIȚ, A., POPOVICI, T., ULIANOVSCHI, GH., ULIANOVSCHI, X., URSU, N., VOLCINSCHI, V. Codul penal al Republicii Moldova: Comentariu. Ch.: Editura Sarmis, 2009, p.310..

From the text of the provision of art. 144 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Moldova, the subject of the cloning offense can be a physical person. Although the Criminal Code of the Republic of Moldova also provides for the legal entity as the subject of the crime, it cannot be held liable for committing the "Cloning" crime.

In accordance with the provisions of art. 3 of Law no. 200 of 16.07.2010 "Regarding the regime of foreigners in the Republic of Moldova", physical persons can also be foreigners, who are defined as "a person who does not hold the citizenship of the Republic of Moldova or who is stateless (who is neither a citizen of the Republic of Moldova and does not have evidence that he possesses the citizenship of another state)".⁶

According to art. 11 (2) Criminal Code of the Republic of Moldova: "Citizens and stateless persons, who live permanently on the territory of the Republic of Moldova and have committed crimes outside the borders of the Republic of Moldova, bear criminal liability in accordance with the Criminal Code."

Foreign citizens and persons without citizenship, who do not live permanently on the territory of the Republic of Moldova and bear criminal liability in accordance with the Criminal Code for committing crimes against the peace and security of mankind and other crimes, provided for by international agreements, one of the parties to which is the Republic of Moldova, if they have not been subject to punishment in a foreign state.⁷

Diplomatic representatives of foreign states and other persons who benefit from diplomatic immunity do not fall under the action of the criminal law of the Republic of Moldova. Immunity, in the case of the crime of cloning, implies the exclusion of the nominated persons from the action of the criminal jurisdiction of the state of residence.

The basis of criminal immunity resides in the provisions of the Vienna Conventions on Diplomatic Relations (1961) and Consular Relations (1963), ratified by the Republic of Moldova, and extends to the diplomatic corps, consuls, members of their families, etc., but only if they are in the exercise of the function. Leaders of special missions and state delegations to bilateral negotiations, international conferences, as well as members of delegations, advisors, experts, etc. benefit from criminal immunity.

In our state, certain categories of citizens benefit from immunity: the President of the country, members of the Parliament, parliamentary lawyers, etc.

In order to be held criminally liable, the physical person must meet several conditions provided by law. Firstly, the physical person must be responsible. In accordance with art. 22 CP of the Republic of Moldova: "responsibility is the psychological state of the person who has the ability to understand the prejudicial character of the act, as well as the ability to manifest his will and direct his actions".⁸ Secondly, the physical person must be of age to be held criminally liable for committing this crime. In accordance with art. 21(1) CP of the Republic of Moldova: "responsible physical persons who, at the time of committing the crime, have reached the age of 16 are liable to criminal liability".⁹

The direct active subject (author) of the examined crime can be any physical person, because for the existence of the crime, the law does not require that the author must be a qualified person, that is, have some quality or fulfill some condition. In this context, some authors consider that the author of the crime can only be a person with a high degree of scientific training in the field of genetics and related sciences.¹⁰

The author V. Boaghi, whose opinion we adhere to, believes that: "in the case of cloning, the subject is special, possessing certain specific qualities, such as: scientific worker, doctor, researcher, i.e. the person who works in this direction".¹¹

The author V. Manea mentions that: "the signs, which characterize the special author, reflect his profession and occupation. This must be a person who possesses knowledge in the field of genetics, molecular biology, reproductive medicine (scientists, collaborators of scientific research institutions, laboratory workers, etc.)".¹²

Authors A.H. Абышева, Жумашева, А.Т. considers that the crime can be committed only by a special subject active in the biomedical field, who, in addition to appropriate studies in the medical or biological field, also possesses a high level of qualification in the scientific field.¹³

Starting from the above, we consider that the crime of cloning could only be committed by a dedicated person - a specialist in the fields of genetics or other related fields, able to achieve the objective side, namely the creation of a human being through cloning. As a result, apart from the mandatory signs provided by the legislation, the respective type of crimes requires the existence of a special subject as an author (co-author). The general subject (or general subjects) can have the role of co-participants.

The position stated above also emerges from the analysis of the regulations related to applied research in

⁶ Legea RM „Privind regimul străinilor în Republica Moldova”: nr. 200 din 16.10.2010. În: Monitorul Oficial al Republicii Moldova.2010, Nr. 179-181 art. 610.

⁷ Codul Penal al Republicii Moldova: Nr. 985 din 18.04.2002. În: Monitorul Oficial al Republicii Moldova, 14.04.2009, nr. 72-74. Art.11

⁸ Codul Penal al Republicii Moldova: Nr. 985 din 18.04.2002. În: Monitorul Oficial al Republicii Moldova, 14.04.2009, nr. 72-74. Art.22

⁹ Codul Penal al Republicii Moldova: Nr. 985 din 18.04.2002. În: Monitorul Oficial al Republicii Moldova, 14.04.2009, nr. 72-74. Art.21

¹⁰ DUNGAN, P. Reglementări în noul Cod penal al României. Crime și delicte privind manipularea genetică. În: Revista de științe penale: Anuarul. 2016. pp.142-149.

¹¹ BOAGHI V. Reflectări juridico-penale privind infracțiunea de clonare. În: Revista Națională de Drept, 2007, nr. 6, p.83.

¹² MANEA, V. Unele aspecte privind problematica analizei juridico-penale a clonării. În: Administrarea publică, nr. 3, 2004, p.159.

¹³ АБЫШЕВА, А.Н., ЖУМАШЕВА, А.Т. Совершенство законодательства РК об ответственности за уголовные правонарушения против чести и достоинства личности. [цитат 25.01.22]. Disponibil: http://www.rusnauka.com/33_IAN_2015/Pravo/5_199581.doc.htm

the field of genetics and microbiology. According to the provisions of point 4 of the Regulation of the Ministry of Health "Regarding the manner of issuing licenses for conducting applied research in the field of genetics and microbiology in the Republic of Moldova", which establishes the circle of persons who can carry out research in the field of genetics and/or microbiology namely: "- holders of a diploma, certificate or certificate issued by a higher or secondary education institution in the respective specialty from the Republic of Moldova or abroad, in the volume and nomenclature, which depends on the post-graduate training in the established manner; - work experience of at least 5 years in this field; - at least category II professional qualification in the field of genetics and/or microbiology."¹⁴ According to point 9 of the Regulation on the provision of medically assisted human reproduction services, approved by Order of the Ministry of Health of Republic of Moldova no. 149 of 23.02.2017: "the medical institution will have the following specialists specializing in performing medically assisted human reproduction techniques: gynecologist, urologist/specialization in andrology, imaging doctor, embryologist, anesthesiologist, medical assistant to the anesthesiologist, nurse medical".¹⁵

Analyzing the provisions of the nominated normative acts, we find that the circle of people who can commit the crime of cloning is quite narrow, and the author, or at least one of the authors, must be a special subject.

In the opinion of the author A.I.Trusov, to which we adhere: "human cloning can be carried out by a plurality of active subjects (co-authors, instigators, accomplices). Most of the time, this type of crime involves co-participation, with a strict division of roles. It would be impossible to commit this crime without the participation of people with experience in the field of molecular genetics or in another field of genetics (transplantology, biological weapons, etc.). Likewise, it would be difficult (practically impossible) to achieve the criminal purpose without adequate funding of such activities. At the same time, these crimes require detailed preparation and cannot be committed spontaneously or in a state of affect, etc. As a result, these crimes involve the participation of a group of people, an organized gang, or even a criminal association".¹⁶

In the opinion of the author V. Manea: "the form of participation in this case is complex (art. 43, art. 45 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Moldova), that is, the participants contribute to the commission of the crime as author, organizer, instigator and accomplice". At the same time, the author admits the intervention of

the participants both through "intellectual complicity (for example, the consultation of the specialist in the field of genetics, molecular biology, obstetrics, etc.) and through physical complicity (for example, the consent of the chief physician of the medical institution to use the room operations, hospital lounges)".¹⁷

At the same time, I do not agree with the opinion of the nominated author, regarding the fact that: "the objective side would always be executed by two or more authors, who can perform the most diverse actions of the objective part of the composition by virtue of the special character of this activities, the mandatory possession of special knowledge and skills". We consider that the crime can be also executed by a single perpetrator.

The Criminal Code of the Republic of Moldova does not provide for the criminal liability of the legal entity for committing the crime of human cloning. De facto, however, the active subject of the analyzed crime could also be the legal entity. Analyzing the provisions of art.1 of the Regulation "Regarding the granting of medically assisted human reproduction services", approved by Order of the Ministry of Health no. 149 of 23.02.2017, we note that: "medically assisted human reproduction services can be granted by medical institutions providing health services of reproduction, authorized and licensed for this type of activity, according to the legislation in force (hereinafter the medical institutions)". According to the provisions of art. 56, 58 of the nominated Regulation: "monitoring and reporting bodies of the above-mentioned activities are the National Transplant Agency and the Center for Reproductive Health and Medical Genetics within the Mother and Child Institute."¹⁸

According to point 3 of the Regulation of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Moldova "Regarding the manner of issuing licenses for conducting applied research in the field of genetics and microbiology in the Republic of Moldova": "the right to a license belongs to physical and legal persons, both domestic and foreign, registered as a subject of the entrepreneurial activity in the Republic of Moldova in the manner established by the legislation, provided that the staff with genetic and/or microbiological activity meets the requirements provided for in point (4), is provided with reagents and certified biological preparations, and in the premises provided for the activity genetic and/or microbiological, all the necessary conditions have been created according to the health legislation in force for this type of activity."¹⁹

¹⁴Regulamentul Ministerului Sănătății al Republicii Moldova "Cu privire la modul de eliberare a licențelor pentru desfășurarea cercetărilor aplicative în domeniul geneticii și microbiologiei în Republica Moldova": Nr. RMS902/2000 din 09.02.2000. În: Monitorul Oficial al Republicii Moldova, 2000, Nr. 054.

¹⁵ Regulamentul „Cu privire la acordarea serviciilor de reproducere umană asistată medical”, aprobat prin Ordinul Ministerului Sănătății nr. 149 din 23.02.2017. [citată 24.01.22]. Disponibil: https://msmps.gov.md/sites/default/files/legislatie/regulament_reproducere_umana_anexa_1.pdf

¹⁶ ТРУСОВ, А. И. Криминологические и уголовно-правовые аспекты предупреждения преступлений, связанных с

использованием биотехнологий: дис. канд. юрид. наук. М., 2011. p. 76

¹⁷ MANEA, V. Unele aspecte privind problematica analizei juridico-penale a clonării. În: Administrarea publică, nr. 3, 2004, p.154.

¹⁸ Regulamentul „Cu privire la acordarea serviciilor de reproducere umană asistată medical”, aprobat prin Ordinul Ministerului Sănătății nr. 149 din 23.02.2017. [citată 24.01.22]. Disponibil: https://msmps.gov.md/sites/default/files/legislatie/regulament_reproducere_umana_anexa_1.pdf

¹⁹ Regulamentul Ministerului Sănătății „Cu privire la modul de eliberare a licențelor pentru desfășurarea cercetărilor aplicative

Analyzing the nominated provisions, we find that the subject of the cloning offense could be autochthonous and foreign physical and legal persons, registered as subjects of entrepreneurial activity in the Republic of Moldova, in the manner established by the legislation, who have a license in the field of genetics and microbiology. In the sense of the above-mentioned rules, it is not considered any physical person, but specifically the physical person whose entrepreneurial activity is registered and has obtained a license for this type of activity. The law on entrepreneurship and enterprises provides for several forms of entrepreneurial activity with the status of a physical person: sole proprietorship, joint venture, limited partnership.²⁰

Apart from the nominated regulations, there are public legal entities, which carry out activities in the field of genetics and microbiology, which in the legislation of other countries cannot be the subject of the respective crime. In the context of the above, according to the provisions of the Criminal Code of Romania, in the 2004 version, was established the liability of legal entities for committing crimes and misdemeanors regarding genetic manipulation, including: "the crime of altering the human genome" (art. 193), "the use of engineering genetics to produce biological weapons or other weapons of mass extermination" (art. 194), "the creation of human embryos for purposes other than procreation and the creation, by cloning, of a human being genetically identical to another human being, living or dead" (art. 195). According to the provisions of art. 197 of the Criminal Code of Romania "Sanctioning of the legal entity", the legal entity is sanctioned for the offenses provided for in this chapter.²¹

The Romanian law "For the prohibition of cloning and applications of biomedicine that violate human rights and human dignity" additionally provides: "the legal dissolution of legal entities under private law that - through their declared or undeclared activities - violate the provisions of this law, from the date of their definitive stay of the court decision of conviction, after the exhaustion of appeals."²² We note that the text of the law cannot be extended to public legal entities.

Starting from the above, we consider it necessary to complete the Criminal Code of the Republic of Moldova with provisions for establishing the liability of the legal entity.

Speaking about the subject of the crime of cloning, it is necessary to determine who is the passive subject or victim of this prejudicial act.

Analyzing the passive subject of the cloning crime, it is necessary to appreciate what is the quality

of the clone. Is the clone merely the product of the cloning process, the material consequence of the crime, or is it a passive subject or victim of the crime.

Some authors consider the clone as a passive subject of the crime, because the harm done to it consists in its creation, a fact by which a possible injury is brought to its human dignity (it can be subject to the opprobrium of society due to the fact that it is stigmatized by its birth; subjection to possible experiments, etc.).²³

The clone cannot be treated as a mere product of the crime of cloning. The clone represents a human being, with all the rights and freedoms that flow from that capacity. At the same time, a lot of issues related to the legal status of the clone remain unclear: if it will have the quality of a citizen, how will it be identified, how will established its paternity and filiation, its patrimonial rights, etc.

We consider the human clone to be a victim of crime of human cloning. By the fact of creation, the clone is harmed, manifested by the damage to dignity and genetic individuality. The author A. Barbăneagra mentions that "the members of a clone are genetically identical, have the same genotype or phenotype, that is, all individuals show the same genetic information: size, behavior, shape, color, physiological functions, chemical composition, internal and external structure, microscopic structure and macroscopic, etc."²⁴

The Romanian author P. Dungan believes that the passive subject of the crime is the human collective subject to the threat of illegally creating human embryos for purposes other than procreation, as well as creating by cloning a human being genetically identical to another human being, living or dead.²⁵

According to the author V. Manea: "the crime of cloning damages, first of all, the society which cannot be qualified as an object or as a victim. If the respective crime causes physical and moral damage to the person (surrogate mother), she can be recognized as a victim (art. 59 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Moldova)". The author argues that she cannot be qualified as a participant in the crime, given the fact that the legislation of the Republic of Moldova grants the woman the right to decide for herself the issue regarding maternity - art. 32 of the Law "On health protection" no. 411-XIII of 28. 03.1995.²⁶

Carrying out a review of the opinions presented in the specialized literature, the passive subject or victim of this kind of crimes can be not only the physical person (clone, surrogate mother, etc.), but the human community itself, the human species, its future. The number of victims of the cloning crime can be high, starting

în domeniul geneticii și microbiologiei în Republica Moldova": Nr. RMS902/2000 din 09.02.2000. În: Monitorul Oficial al Republicii Moldova, 2000, Nr. 054.

²⁰ Legea RM „Cu privire la antreprenoriat și întreprinderi”: Nr. 845 din 03-01-1992. În: Monitorul Parlamentului, 1994, Nr. 2, art. 14-16.

²¹ Sancționarea persoanei juridice. Extras din Codul Penal al României. [citată 25.01.22]. Disponibil: <https://lege5.ro/Gratuit/gu3dgobt/art-197-sanctionarea-persoanei-juridice-codul-penal?dp=gi2tcnbygq4ds>

²² Legea României „Pentru interzicerea clonării și a aplicațiilor biomedicinii care încalcă drepturile omului și

demnitatea umană”. [citată 25.01.21]. Disponibil: <http://www.senat.ro/Legis/PDF/2010/10L464FS.pdf>.

²³ MUTU, M. Aspecte generale privind clonarea ființei umane. În: Revista Națională de Drept, 2004, nr. 1, p.22

²⁴ BARBĂNEAGRĂ, A. Clonarea ființelor umane. În: Revista Națională de Drept, 2005, Nr.11, pp.8-15

²⁵ DUNGAN, P. Reglementări în noul Cod penal al României. Crime și delicate privind manipularea genetică. În: Revista de științe penale: Anuarul. 2016. pp.142-149.

²⁶ MANEA V. Unele aspecte privind problematica analizei juridico-penale a clonării. În: Administrarea publică, nr. 3, 2004, p.154.

from the risks of cloning, which can generate the formation of a population of individuals who could suffer from the same diseases or malformations, and a single virus could exterminate the entire population. At the same time, establishing the number of victims of the crime of human cloning will be a difficult process, because concrete measures are required to assess the impact of these facts on the environment, on individuals and on society as a whole.

Concluzions

1. The subject of the crime of cloning can be any responsible physical person who has reached the age of 16, regardless of whether he is a citizen of the Republic of Moldova, a foreign citizen or a person without citizenship.

2. The crime of human cloning could be committed by a special subject (perpetrator), as a result, the incriminating text need to be modified, in the sense of introducing the aggravating factor that would regulate the criminal liability of the special subject or the commission of this crime with the use of the service situation.

3. The legal person may be subject to the crime of cloning, as a result it is necessary to amend and supplement the Criminal Code of the Republic of Moldova, in the sense of establishing the liability of the legal entity.

4. The clone is one of the passive subjects of the crime, however the passive subject or victim of this kind of crimes can be not only the physical person (clone, surrogate mother, etc.), but the human community itself, the human species, its future.

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